

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Data Management Plan

Document Information

Report name	Data Management Plan
Version number	4.0
Document number	D1.4
Due date for deliverable	30/11/2021
Actual submission date	30/11/2021
Lead beneficiary	UPC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

DOCUMENT CONTROL PAGE

Author	Fernando Sanahuja Diago/ Dominik Jasinski
Version number	4.0
Date	29/11/2021
Modified by	Luis Romeral/ Eva Urbano/ Victor Martinez/ Marta Crespi
Comments	
Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Submitted
	<input type="checkbox"/> Accepted
Action requested	<input type="checkbox"/> To be revised
	Deadline for action: No action

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Date	Version	Prepared by	Organization	Notes
15/11/2017	V01	Fernando Sanahuja	Exergy Ltd (EXE)	
30/11/2017	V02	Fernando Sanahuja	Exergy Ltd (EXE)	
15/02/2019	V03	Dominik Jasinski	Exergy Ltd (EXE)	
30/11/2021	V04	Luis Romeral/ Eva Urbano/ Victor Martinez/ Marta Crespi	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the ECOBULK project, funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant Agreement number 730456. The purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy and to describe the data management life cycle for all data sets collected, processed or generated by ECOBULK. This document provides a general overview of the nature of the research data collected and generated and outlines how these data has been handled during the project. The DMP presents in detail the procedure for the management of datasets created during the lifetime of the project and describes the key data management principles, notably in terms of data standards and metadata, sharing, archiving and preservation.

This first version of the DMP was developed in M6 and was updated in M21 following the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" (Version 3.0, 26th July 2016). In this version, submitted at the end of the ECOBULK project, the results on data management are exposed, including the procedures followed and obtained data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described in this document was subsidised by the European Community Horizon 2020 through the Grant Agreement Number 730456.

DISCLAIMER

This document reflects only the author's' view and not those of the European Community. This work may rely on data from sources external to the members of the ECOBULK project Consortium. Members of the Consortium do not accept liability for loss or damage suffered by any third party as a result of errors or inaccuracies in such data. The information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at its sole risk and neither the European Community nor any member of the ECOBULK Consortium is liable for any use that may be made of the information.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	4
DISCLAIMER	4
1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. DATA MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES	7
3. DATA SUMMARY	8
3.1. PURPOSE OF DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION	8
3.2. DATA GATHERING AND RE-USE ANALYSIS BEFORE PROJECT EXECUTION	11
3.2.1. <i>Data types and formats</i>	11
3.2.2. <i>Data origin</i>	13
3.2.3. <i>Data size</i>	14
3.2.4. <i>Data utility</i>	14
3.2.5. <i>Data re-use</i>	16
3.3. DATA GATHERED AND RE-USED DURING THE PROJECT	16
3.3.1. <i>Data generation</i>	16
3.3.2. <i>Data re-use</i>	24
4. FAIR DATA	26
4.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA.....	26
4.1.1. <i>Making data discoverable and identifiable</i>	26
4.1.2. <i>Metadata and naming convention</i>	28
4.2. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE	29
4.2.1. <i>Open access to scientific publications</i>	30
4.2.2. <i>Open access to other data</i>	31
4.2.3. <i>Data storage</i>	31
4.3. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE	32
4.4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE (THROUGH CLARIFYING LICENCES)	33
4.4.1. <i>Re-use of data</i>	34
4.4.2. <i>Data quality assurance</i>	34

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	35
6. DATA SECURITY	36
7. ETHICAL ASPECTS	37
ANNEX A: DATA IN ZENODO	38

1. INTRODUCTION

The Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how the data collected through the whole project is generated, treated and processed to make it FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable). Within a H2020 project, data management is a key element and the “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” have been followed during the development of this DMP, which includes information on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project;
- what data is collected, processed and/or generated;
- which methodology and standards are applied;
- whether data is shared/made open access and;
- how data is curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

In Horizon 2020, the Commission has launched a flexible pilot for open access to research data (ORD pilot). The pilot aims at improving and maximising access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects, taking into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and IPR, privacy concerns, security, data management and preservation questions. All projects participating in the extended ORD pilot, including ECOBULK, are required to have a DMP, detailing what data the project generates, whether and how it is exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it is curated and preserved.¹ The present document exposes the ECOBULK DMP and the results obtained over the project.

2. DATA MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES

The development of the DMP for ECOBULK permits the consortium partners to deal with all issues regarding data management. Even though the DMP was a Deliverable due in Month 6 (D1.5), it has been updated throughout the project. The responsible for DMP and its updates in ECOBULK is the project coordinator, which was EXERGY until M36 and UPC from then until the end of the project.

The consortium complies with the requirements of **Regulation (EU) 2016/679** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 which entered into force on May 25th 2018 on

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

the “*protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data*” (General Data Protection Regulation), and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. The Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement are to be referred to regarding type of data, storage, recruitment process, confidentiality, ownership, management of intellectual property and access. The specific articles from the Grant Agreement of importance for this issue are Articles 18, 23a, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 36, 39 and 52 and “Annex I – Description of the Action” of the Grant Agreement. The Grant Agreement was signed on 02/05/2017 while the Consortium Agreement was set into force on 24/05/2017.

The procedures for data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction are in line with the mentioned Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and EU standards, and “*where this Regulation provides for specifications or restrictions of its rules by Member State law, Member States may, as far as necessary for coherence and for making the national provisions comprehensible to the persons to whom they apply, incorporate elements of this Regulation into their national law*” [Legislative acts (8) EU 2016/679].

An ethical approach has been adopted and maintained throughout the fieldwork process. The Steering Committee and responsible partners have ensured that the EU standards regarding Data Management are fulfilled and each partner has proceeded with the data management according to the provisions of the Regulation for Data Management and Ethics.

3. DATA SUMMARY

3.1. Purpose of data collection/generation

The main purpose of collecting and generating the data is to be able to carry out the tasks pursuing the achievement of the project objectives, and ensuring sustainability, high quality, profitability and social benefits of the proposed circular economy set up for three industrial systems. The data is intended for providing streamlined and cooperative workflow comprising all features of the data lifecycle, involving data acquisition, manipulation and analysis, experimental planning, data storage, Open access and FAIR principles. The purpose of data collection/generation in relation to the specific project objectives is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 The purpose of data collection/generation in relation to ECOBULK objectives

Objectives	Purpose for data collection
Objective 1: Develop the Design Circular framework and redesign supply and value chains for composite products for internal car parts, furniture and building components	Data has been collected within Task 2.2 (D2.2) as well as Task 2.4 (D2.4) for the (re-)design process of the carrier products. These data comprise interviews and workshops results, as well as observations regarding the design process.
Objective 2: Develop and implement a Database Management Plan, an innovative Quality Assurance System, and Tracking and Labelling Systems	Data collection in relation to Objectives 2 and 3 have been performed in WP6, and it refers to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the necessity to acquire sufficient data to support both the design and implementation of the software systems developed within the framework of the project (D6.1, D6.2 and D6.4); and 2) the establishment of dependency of the correct operation of the software systems on the context and expectations of the user (D6.3, D6.4, D6.5 and D6.6)
Objective 3: Develop and implement an end-user and stakeholder platform and strategies to encourage shifting towards the circular economy model	
Objective 4: Demonstrate the implementation of the circular economy concept and framework in solutions for automotive, furniture, and building components sectors	Data collection has been carried out with the aim to obtain social information for the product design as well as behaviour and feedback from the end users in DEMO activities. Surveys and structured interviews have been conducted to end-users and other stakeholders (e.g. manufacturers, consumers) of the DEMO activities to obtain social, economic and environmental

	information related to the design of the products.
Objective 5: Validate solutions for collection, sorting and pre-treatments of current heterogeneous Bulky and ELV waste streams for material recovering, integration and revalorization into ECOBULK's circular economy model	Data generated in WP5 regarding the recovery and characterisation of materials from the current heterogeneous MBW and ELV waste streams.
Objective 6: Develop and validate innovative business models and an exploitation strategy to translate products and services along the entire ECOBULK's circular concept into attractive value propositions	Customer behaviour, market, economic and IP data has been collected in WP8 in order to develop and validate new business models, identify barriers preventing the transition towards circular economy, understand customer behaviour, and develop exploitation and business plans for the project.
Objective 7: Demonstrate the economic, social and environmental sustainability of the proposed supply and value chain	In order to ensure the sustainability and profitability of the proposed circular economy products, data regarding materials and energy flows, economic flows (e.g. CAPEX and OPEX), and other social impacts have been collected in WP7.
Objective 8: Address the barriers to facilitate the transition towards circular economy and assess side-effects and risks of the products	Semi-structured interviews and workshops with the value chain partners within ECOBULK have been conducted in WP8 to fulfil this objective.
Objective 9: Maximise promotion and impacts of the project results on the target market and contribute to the creation of new jobs and training	Email addresses for the ECOBULK mailing list have been collected for the purpose of sending out newsletters and any periodic announcements as necessary to keep people

	informed about the ECOBULK project, specifically in WP9 (T9.2).
--	---

3.2. Data gathering and re-use analysis before project execution

3.2.1. Data types and formats

An important distinction should be made between various forms of data collected, generated and utilized within ECOBULK:

- (a) **Experimental and observational data** (*regarding the design, technologies and demo sites*). This is essentially the data collected through the instruments used in the design process, technology development and testing (experimental data resulting from material characterisation and a range of technology tests in ECOBULK) and demonstration sites' activities.
- (b) **Derived data**. It is the data derived from the experimental and observational data, and targets at making comparisons between experimental results and conditions, facilitates drawing conclusions and permits other uses and reuses of the data. This data can be stored in many formats, as can be spreadsheets or Word documents.
- (c) **Survey and interview data**: data collected from a targeted group of people about their opinions, behaviour or knowledge. Common types of example surveys are written questionnaires, face-to-face or telephone interviews, focus groups and electronic (e-mail or Web site) surveys. This data is collected in ECOBULK for the design process (WP2), definition of circular business models and understanding customer behaviour (WP8) and from the user experience studies regarding the demo pilot products (WP4).
- (d) **Simulations**. Involving computing simulations of the models and tests for assessing the optimisation of, for example, energy consumption, economic data, performance of reverse logistics models, etc., to assure that all elements of the ECOBULK Circular Economy framework have been tested and validated within the time line of the project.
- (e) **Software**. Data integrated into and conforming the commercially exploitable software products of the project, i.e. Granta's online platform for material selection for product design and development, End-users and Stakeholder Platform, Decision Supporting System (DSS) and Quality Assurance System (QAS). ECOBULK database and supporting digital systems is developed in WP6 to collect and analyse the data obtained from the

circular supply chain, offering functionalities to support and promote the circularity of products and materials.

- (f) **Multimedia documents.** Data aimed at presenting other data and associated with formal publications, such as journal applications. This type of data can be reports, spread sheets, presentations, websites, etc.
- (g) **Interactive data.** Data put in the context of other data e.g. integrated with other data sets. Interactive data enhances the possibility of data reuse since it boosts its availability.
- (h) **Images.** Photos documenting the progress of the project, for example, from the demonstration facilities to explain how the tests are being made; from the technologies to show their composition and structure; or from events and meetings of the project partners.
- (i) **Videos.** Video-recorded interview data and presentations in form of videos, short movies or animations, explaining and showing facilities, technologies, equipment, progresses, tasks and/or results coming from the project.

Formats of the data are as follow:

- (a) Microsoft Office file format and .pdf files are the reference for documents, text, tables, presentations, Excel-/data-sheets, etc. (a, b, c, d, g types as defined above).
- (b) Data coming from measurements are filed in original format - depending from the sensor/application used to get the measure - and exported to ASCII file using TXT and CSV format (a).
- (c) Images are stored in JPEG and TIFF formats (h).
- (d) Videos are stored in MP4 (i).
- (e) The software itself is stored as plain text and compiled binaries (e), whereas the data integrated in the software products is collected in various formats, as presented in Table 2:

Table 2 Data type and their format for ECOBULK digital services, systems and platforms

Name	Description	Format
Waste or raw material	Data from material producers and waste handlers regarding the properties, amount and quality of the materials produced.	Text and -media (images, video).

Name	Description	Format
Components or products	Information about the properties, design, materials used, etc. to produce these components or products.	Text, media (images, video) or other graphic support.
Processes	Data derived from the processes performed to obtain the materials or products aforementioned.	Text, images and videos.
Test Data / QA	Data series from the processes or tests applied to the materials / products.	Text and media (images, videos, audio, etc.).
Design data	Several information about the design including drawings, reports and feedback.	Text files and media.
Market Data / Supply chain	Information about material producers, product manufacturers, suppliers, collection and repairing sites and feedback from the different actors.	Text, geospatial and/or images
User personal information	User information like the platform login credentials and profile information (address, kind of business, etc.).	Text and media.
Product tracking and labelling	Information for the tracking of the product including QR code and associated data.	Text and images.

3.2.2. Data origin

The data exposed in the previous section is produced by various partners and derived from different sources throughout the project including interviews, workshops, laboratory trials, tests and experiments, observational analysis, etc. The potential data origins were identified at the beginning of the project. In this section, this first analysis is exposed. The data generated through the project and its origin is exposed in upcoming sections, specifically in 3.3.1. Thus, the information below reflects the information gathered from the consortium at the beginning of the project regarding potential data origins:

- User Stories, Use Cases and other information supporting the design and implementation of the software systems in WP6 obtained from users and

stakeholders of the project in the form of questionnaires and meetings focused on collecting feedback – **Granta, UPC, IRIS, Exergy, ITENE.**

- User details, context and preconditions necessary for the proper operation of the functionalities of the stakeholders' platform developed in WP6 collected during the operation of the software systems. The data may originate from several sources, including provided directly by users or obtained from dependent systems - **UPC.**
- Surveys, interviews and workshops for WP2 and WP8 – **TU Delft, Oakdene Hollins, KNEIA, UNE.**
- Lab trials, tests, experiments in WP3, WP4 and WP5 – **KEAS, NTT, Tomra, Conenor, IRIS, Tecnar, Netcomposites, AkzoNobel, Cranfield, Warwick, Coventry, Moretti, MAIER, CRF, MicroCab, AIMPLAS, CNR, Bellver, ITENE, Technoplants, LIPOR.**
- Data for economic, environmental and social assessment collected from technology developers, demo site managers and other involved stakeholders – **FCBA, UPC, AIMPLAS.**
- Emails collected through the ECOBULK website, using the standard double opt-in model and a procedure to fulfil the necessary obligations regarding deletions and provision of all data held by the website.– **ISWA.**

3.2.3. Data size

Given the different sources and types of the data collected, at the beginning of the project the total amount of data obtained and managed in ECOBULK was expected to be within a minimum of a several gigabytes and a maximum of a few terabytes. These data includes raw, analytical and metadata, and the software systems to support the project's actions. The final size of data is exposed in section 3.3.1.

3.2.4. Data utility

The ultimate goal of making the data FAIR is for it to be reachable and accessible to all stakeholders interested in the circular economy concept and composites. The developments and data generated in ECOBULK should serve as useful information for the development of other tools and services that contribute to the common purpose of improving the circularity and sustainability of composite materials and products. On the one hand, the data and publications developed in the project will be useful to other research projects in the same field and sectors

(automotive, furniture and construction). On the other hand, the results from ECOBULK are expected to demonstrate a high potential of cross-sectorial replicability and transferability to other sectors as well, providing evidence-based knowledge for enabling framework conditions (such as the regulatory or policy framework) that facilitate a broader transition to the circular economy in the EU. Specific data utility in the project was outlined at the beginning of the project in the first DMP, and is exposed in the following points:

Data collected from demo sites is useful mainly for the members of the consortium participating in WP2 (in relation to prototype development and testing of circular design tools and strategies); WP3 (demonstrating the technical feasibility of the developed materials for the product application); WP5 (in relation to the possibility of recycling incorporating composite materials coming from the current linear systems); WP6 (to support the design and implementation of the software systems, so that the implemented functions and features match the requirements of users and stakeholders); WP7 (regarding KPI definition and analysis of sustainability); and WP8 (in relation with activities aimed at the assessment of business opportunities and business models supporting the circularity of composite materials and products, as well as preparation of the exploitation plan). This data is also useful to demonstrate the viability of circular economy for other researchers, OEMs and for the general public.

The outcome of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Cos (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA), from WP7, exposes the environmental impacts of the proposed modular ECOBULK demonstrators with respect to the benchmark technologies. The costs for implementation and operation are compared in order to determine the overall economic feasibility of bringing these products (and associated technologies) to the market with the consideration of different, more circular business models. The results from the S-LCA represent input to stimulate preferences for the new circular demonstrator products, value chains and business models. This data is valuable for researchers and specially for OEMs interested in implementing circular economy solutions.

- The ECOBULK database platform, services and systems is useful for public and private decision makers and actors, by providing performance and operational data obtained from product designs, repair, remanufacture and recycle processes and secondary raw material production involved in a circular supply chain. The software system is also

useful for end-users looking for circular products and trying to enhance the circularity of their owned products.

- The opportunities of ECOBULK will be demonstrated throughout the entire supply and value chain: from the product design until the end of life of the product. ECOBULK will demonstrate the replicability of project technologies, processes and outcomes for circular solutions and models, which will create business opportunities for other products and sector, not directly linked with the three industrial lines targeted in the project. This data is useful mainly to OEMs innovating in their products and supply chains.

3.2.5. Data re-use

To fulfil ECOBULK objectives and propose relevant advances, the following data is considered for re-use: high quality curated peer-reviewed published data, data disclosed in public repositories data, information from similar marketed tools, field-related data, and any type or information, publicly available, that could be useful for the successful achievement of the project activities. The data re-use planning developed at the beginning of the project (first DMP version) included a pool of historical data to compare the current with the future values of given parameters coming from various tests on products, components and materials. Data from literature source was also considered to be introduced in the sustainable assessments. Existing data, available in public repositories or from institutional partners were planned to be re-used, whenever possible, to better understand the specifications and requirements for the products and materials development and manufacturing. The data that has been re-used during the project execution is exposed in 3.3.2.

3.3. Data gathered and re-used during the project

During the project execution, the guidelines exposed in the previous section have been followed in order to gather information in a structured manner and enabling its inter-operability and accessibility. In this section, the specific data generated and re-used in ECOBULK is exposed.

3.3.1. Data generation

In Table 3, the summary of data collected in the ECOBULK project is exposed. The data generated is exposed together with its origin, type, format, size and utility.

Table 3: Data generated in ECOBULK

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
Minutes and videos of project's meeting	WP1: SC meetings, General Assembly and Review meetings.	Text	PDF, MP4	2000MB	Project consortium and Project Officer	UPC
General Assembly presentations	WP1: General Assembly	Text	PDF	574MB	Project consortium and Project Officer	UPC
Connection and fasteners for circularity	WP2 derived data through literature review and creation of circularity indicators	Software and Text	Text and binary	3MB	Project consortium	TU DELFT
Prototype's design	WP2 through interviews with project manufacturers and analysis of social, environmental and technical circularity implications.	Text, Images, Drawings	PDF	11MB	Project consortium	TU DELFT, WARWICK UNIVERSITY, LIPOR, MORETTI, GRANTA

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
Properties, costs and energy consumption of new materials	WP3 experimental tests	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet and PDF	7MB	Project consortium	NTT, COVENTIVE, TECNARO, MAIER, CONENOR, TECHNOPLANTS
Re-manufacturability /re-cyclability of new materials	WP3 experimental tests	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet, PDF, Images and Video	220MB	Project consortium	CNR, AIMPLAS, NTT, COVENTIVE, TECNARO, CONENOR
Re-manufacturability with new binder for wooden products	WP3 experimental tests	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet	60kB	Project consortium	AKZONOBEL, KEAS, CRANFIELD
Material conditioning and preparation results with novel technologies	WP3 experimental tests	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet and PDF	60kB	Project consortium, Researchers, OEMs	NTT, IRIS
Manufacturing and re-manufacturing of circular parts/components	WP4 manufacturing tasks	Text	Spreadsheet, PDF, Images and Videos	690MB	Project consortium	MAIER, WARWICK, MORETTI, CRANFIELD, NTT, COVENTRY

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
Performance and durability of circular parts/components	WP4 experimental tests	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet, PDF and Images	820MB	Project consortium	MAIER, CRF, MORETTI, WARWICK, MICROCAB, MORETTI
Manufacturers and users' feedback regarding new circular products	WP4 and WP6 questionnaires	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet and PDF	5MB	Project consortium	LIPOR, WARWICK, COVENTRY, FCBA, MICROCAB, CONENOR, MAIER, CRF, MORETTI UPC
Recovery of materials analysis	WP5 experimental tests	Video	MP4	48MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	BELLVER, ITENE
Waste stream characterization	WP5 experimental tests	Numeric and Text	Spreadsheet and PDF	10MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	TOMRA

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
End-User and Stakeholder Platform, including materials, parts and products' data	WP6 software development	Software and Text	Text	24MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	UPC
Decision Support System	WP6 software development	Software and Text	Text	11MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	UPC
Quality Assurance System	WP6 software development	Software and Text	Text	15MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	IRIS
LCA / LCC / CBA and S-LCA data	WP7 life cycle analysis	Numeric	Spreadsheet	5MB	Project consortium	FCBA, UPC, AIMPLAS
Interviews with representative actors of the supply chain	WP8 benchmarking and assessments	Text	PDF	2MB	Project consortium	OH

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
CWA 17806:2021	WP8 and WP5 standardization activities	Text	PDF	3MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	UNE, ITENE, BELLVER, UPC
CWA 17807:2021	WP8 and WP5 standardization activities	Text	PDF	4MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	UNE, ITENE, BELLVER, UPC
ECOBULK presentation video	WP9 dissemination activities	Video	MP4	17MB	Project consortium, Researchers and OEMs.	ISWA
ECOBULK final results video	WP9 dissemination activities	Video	MP4	20MB	Researchers, OEMs and general public	ISWA

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
Final conference materials	WP9 dissemination activities	Video, Text	MP4 and PDF	900MB	Researchers, OEMs and general public	ISWA
Project leaflet	WP9 dissemination activities	Text and Images	PDF	6MB	Researchers, OEMs and general public	KNEIA
Informational factsheet	WP9 dissemination activities	Text and Images	PDF	1MB	Researchers, OEMs and general public	KNEIA
Interviews with project partners	WP9 dissemination activities	Video	MP4	57MB	Researchers, OEMs and general public	ISWA
Massive Open Online Courses	WP9 training activities	Video	Video	200MB	Researchers, OEMs and general public	ISWA
Deliverables	All WPs developments	Text	PDF	165MB	Project consortium,	All

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

Dataset	Origin	Type	Format	Size	Utility	Partners
					researchers and OEMs.	
Periodic reports	All WPs developments	Text	PDF	22MB	Project consortium,	UPC
Scientific publications	All WPs developments	Text	PDF	50MB	Project consortium, researchers and OEMs.	All
Dissemination and communication publications (forums, meetings, etc.)	All WPs developments	Text	PDF	100MB	Project consortium, researchers and OEMs.	All

3.3.2. Data re-use

The data from external sources that has been re-used in the ECOBULK project is exposed in Table 4.

Table 4 Data re-used by ECOBULK

WP	Data
WP1	National and international funding sources European Commission guidelines for H2020 projects
WP2	Social, environmental, and economic parameters for design according to the literature Legislation standards Partners' current designs Materials characteristics Manufacturing technologies characteristics and requirements Joints, connections, and fasteners solutions
WP3	Properties and energy consumption, costs and re-manufacturability characteristics of existent materials Existent binders' properties and costs Literature review on pre-treatment processes
WP4	Standards and legislation Non-circular products characteristics
WP5	Characteristics, costs and limitations of existent logistic strategies Characteristics, costs and limitations of current dismantling strategies Characteristics, cost of treatment and recovery value of current waste streams
WP6	Product tracking strategies Review of decision support systems Standards applicable to project materials and prototypes
WP7	Life-cycle non-circular product information Economic, social, and environmental data obtained from Ecoinvent v3 and SimaPro Regulations and health and safety requirements for products
WP8	Existent supply chain characteristics Current market situation Current possible exploitation routes SPIRE PPP Roadmap Existent standardization landscape

4. FAIR DATA

FAIR data principles are organised into four categories: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable. Those principles relate to the characteristics that the data should have to enhance their value and impact on society and for other related researches and studies. This section discusses in details the FAIR data principles in relation to the ECOBULK project.

4.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1. Making data discoverable and identifiable

The first principle of the FAIR is making the data Findable, for which any data object should be uniquely and persistently identifiable. Furthermore, the data object should be re-findable at any given point in time, therefore data objects should be persistent, with emphasis on their metadata. A data object should be identifiable through basic machine actionable metadata that allows it to be distinguished from other data. Thus, data identifiers should be unique and persistent.² To this aim, the specific principles to make the data findable for scientific data management are determined:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource³

In order to fulfil the “Findable data” principles, ECOBULK makes use of a data repository to store the collected and generated data, which facilitates the accessing and finding of data sets and tools by the Consortium and by external entities or individuals. This repository is Zenodo⁴, a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). An ECOBULK community has been created in Zenodo, where all the information generated in the project is being uploaded. This community is available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/ecobulk>.

² The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarships, *Guiding Principles for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable Data Publishing Version B1.0*, see <https://www.force11.org/fairprinciples>

³ Wilkinson M.D. et al., 2016. *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*, see <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

⁴ Data repository developed and hosted by CERN, see zenodo.org

Each data set in Zenodo is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), which is a persistent identifier used to identify objects uniquely and standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). The employment of a DOI for the data generated presents a robust system for identifying the information and tracking their use in other activities. The DOI system is designed for interoperability; that is to use, or work with, existing identifier and metadata schemes. Unique identifiers are essential for the management of information in any digital environment. Identifiers assigned in one context may be encountered, and may be re-used, in another place (or time) without consulting the assigner, who cannot guarantee that his assumptions will be known to someone else. Persistence of an identifier can be considered an extension of this concept: interoperability with the future. Moreover, since the services outside the direct control of the issuing assigner are by definition arbitrary, interoperability implies the requirement of extensibility. Hence the DOI system is designed as a generic framework applicable to any digital object, providing a structured, extensible means of identification, description and resolution.⁵ For those data sets that already have a DOI before their upload to Zenodo, such as journal articles, the first assigned DOI is maintained and introduced to Zenodo to avoid duplication. Zenodo also allows to update data sets with new versions when these arise, maintaining a version control and permitting to navigate through the versions, which have different DOI and are clearly identified, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Version control and DOIs.

⁵ http://www.doi.org/doi_handbook/1_Introduction.html#1.6.1

To further ease data discoverability and identification while optimising the possibilities of data re-use, a set of search keywords have been included with the data. The most common keywords employed for the data generated are: Automotive, Material Characterization, GFRP, Circular Design, Circular Economy, and Decision Support.

Apart from Zenodo, the ECOBULK webpage (<https://www.ecobulk.eu/>) is employed for sharing the final public reports and documentation of the project, including also all dissemination and communication activities.

4.1.2. Metadata and naming convention

Metadata enables other researchers to find data in an online repository and is, as such, essential for the reusability of the dataset. By adding rich and detailed metadata, other researchers, can better determine whether the dataset is relevant and useful for their own research. In the repository used by ECOBULK, metadata has been uploaded in a standardized form following the DateCite Metadata Schema⁶. This metadata has been kept separate from the original raw research data. The minimum metadata included for each of the data sets are:

- Title
- Project
- Authors: Name and organization
- Publication date
- Description
- Language
- Keywords
- Funding, including Grant.

Apart from these metadata, formal reports have been formatted such that their frontpage uniformly contains the following relevant information: name of the project, GA number, name of the report, version, number of formal report or deliverable, lead author, due date for submission, and actual submission date. A frontpage example can be seen in Figure 2.

⁶ <https://schema.datacite.org/>

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Report on development of nonwovens intermediate products

Document Information

Report name	Report on development of nonwovens intermediate products
Version number	4.0
Document number	D3.2
Due date for deliverable	31/05/2019
Actual submission date	30/05/2019
Lead beneficiary	NTT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

Figure 2: Deliverable's frontpage structure and data

In addition to the metadata specified for each of the datasets and the information included in them, the datasets are named according to the naming convention agreed in the ECOBULK project, which is:

ECOBULK_<Partner responsible of the data>_<Data set name>.<extension>

4.2. Making data openly accessible

The principle of making the data openly accessible is achieved by following the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research data in Horizon 2020⁷ for the management

⁷ European Commission, 2017. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, see

of the project data and documents. Therefore, and to maximise public and researcher approachability, open access has been granted to all scientific publications resulting from the project. These data and associated metadata generated in the project have been made accessible by deposition in the Zenodo online repository. Aside from scientific publications, data obtained through the project has been reviewed and presented in a suitable way to make it open access, in line with the EU guidelines. The results of the project can thus be disseminated faster and more widely, to the benefit of researchers, innovative industry, and citizens. Some data has been maintained restricted to the ECOBULK consortium for Open Access not to interfere with legitimate interests of the partners in terms of data protection and IPR issues related to commercial impacts of project outcomes. Nonetheless, these data have been transformed and presented in a suitable manner in reports, presentations, and publications to allow its dissemination maintaining its confidentiality.

4.2.1. Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary of the project has ensured open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Access includes not only basic elements, the right to read, download and print, but also the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine.¹⁰ In particular, all beneficiaries had to:

- (a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications (“green open access”).
- (b) ensure open access to the deposited publication, via the repository, at the latest:
 - (i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - (ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- (c) ensure open access, via the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata should follow the DateCite Metadata Schema.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

4.2.2. Open access to other data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries have:

- (a) deposited it in the data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) the following:
 - (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in, scientific publications as soon as possible;
 - (ii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in this 'data management plan' (see Annex 1 of Grant Agreement);
- (b) provided information, via the repository, about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and, where possible, provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39 of the Grant Agreement, all of which still apply. Beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their data if the achievement of the action's main objective would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. Nonetheless, restricted data will be uploaded in the online repository and metadata will be included, the latter being openly accessible. The data generated in ECOBULK which is open and the data that has been kept confidential can be consulted in: <https://zenodo.org/communities/ecobulk>. The table with all the datasets uploaded to Zenodo is also available in Annex A: Data in Zenodo, exposing their DOI and access rights, among other information.

4.2.3. Data storage

Data generated in ECOBULK are deposited in the Zenodo repository. Data formats include .pdf, presentations, spreadsheets, images in JPEG or TIFF, and MP4 videos. These formats are accessible with general use software with open access versions which are therefore not included in the repository. In order to upload all the data to Zenodo following the guidelines provided in this document, a data access committee in ECOBULK was generated formed by members of UPC, the coordination entity. In the employed repository, all metadata for individual records can be

harvested using the OAI-PMH protocol, and metadata is also retrievable through a public REST API⁸. These are open, free and universal protocols which are widely used for information retrieval and thus maximize the accessibility of the data. All the metadata is publicly accessible and licensed under public domain and no authorization is necessary to retrieve it. Open-access data is also retrievable, and it is licensed through Creative Commons to improve its usability. The lifetime of data and metadata is that of the repository. Currently, Zenodo's lifetime is that of CERN, which has a defined programme for the next 20 years. As metadata and data are stored separately in high-availability database servers at CERN, metadata will be accessible even if data is no longer available due to external reasons.

4.3. Making data interoperable

The principle of interoperability is based on the ability of systems and services that create, exchange and consume data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data.⁹ It allows the data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort. This principle prescribes that data must be sufficiently annotated such that people can understand what the data means, thus, a clear data format must be used, values must have units, columns must have clear annotation what was measured, etc. This is also where ontologies (vocabularies) typically come in. To be interoperable, the principles specify:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

For two systems to be interoperable, they must be able to exchange data and subsequently present that data such that it can be understood by a user. Implementing data interoperability requires realising data integration and data exchange as well as enabling effective use of the data that becomes available. The selected open repository uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers exports to two other common formats: Dublin Core¹⁰ and

⁸ <https://developers.zenodo.org/>

⁹ <http://www.grdi2020.eu/Repository/FileScaricati/c4fb6ab0-d83b-49ae-ab14-6d8030fc2422.pdf>

¹⁰ <http://dublincore.org/>

MARCXML¹¹. These international standards are used for storage and interoperability of research information, and comprise a concept about research entities, their description, formalization and relationships. Also, ECOBULK makes use of standard vocabularies for all data types present in the data sets to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability. The metadata related to license, funders, and grants are specified following the vocabularies established by Open Definition¹², FundRef¹³, and OpenAIRE¹⁴, respectively.

In each data set standard vocabularies are included for all data types exposed, detailing their concept and unit of measurement where apply. Additionally, used external data employed in the development of the dataset is referenced through relevant metadata.

4.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The ultimate objective of FAIR is to optimise the re-use of data. To attain this, data and metadata should be properly characterised so that they can be reproduced and/or combined in diverse settings.¹⁵ The principle of re-using the data is directly related to interoperability, since this last concept enables data exchange. In several frameworks, a high percentage of the data value is linked to the possibility of data re-use. To this aim, making available an extensive set of information about the data and its background is essential to foster replicability in the project's same field. Moreover, it is important to clarify the characteristics of this set information, the format in which it will be represented and the manner that this information should be communicated. To be Reusable, the principle specifies:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

¹¹ <https://www.loc.gov/marc/marcxml.html>

¹² <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>

¹³ <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

¹⁴ <https://develop.openaire.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

4.4.1. Re-use of data

ECOBULK promotes free and open data sharing in line with the Open Research Data Pilot. The project's open collected and generated data has been included in the Zenodo repository and is available publicly. A licence has been assigned to each open dataset to enhance their re-use. The chosen licence is the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY-4.0). The domain of the licence is the content and the data itself and it requires attribution for the re-use of data but does not force to share-alike¹⁶. As commented in section 4.2, all scientific publications are published openly and, in the case of ECOBULK, no embargo has been required for any of them. Research data has been also reviewed and significant results and contributions made public for re-use under licence CC-BY-4.0. Regarding data availability, datasets are published immediately after the date of publication of the associated scientific article as commented in section 4.2.1, whereas reports and associated data are available immediately after the submission of the related deliverable. Open data in the project can be accessed by third parties and will be available beyond the project end through the employed open online repository. Currently, the expected lifetime of the data is of 20 years, as exposed in section 4.2.3.

4.4.2. Data quality assurance

All project documentation including deliverables, reports, presentations, etc, has been reviewed by the responsible WP partner with the final approval of Project Coordinator. Regarding research data obtained from tests, the following two steps have also been followed to ascertain the quality of the data against errors:

- Data completeness: data has been analysed onsite in order to get immediate feedback on issues such as incomplete data, missing data, out-of-range values and logical/physical inconsistencies.
- Data consistency: each experiment has been characterized in terms of accuracy and precision of the significant data measured during the test.. No data without information on consistency has been considered for technical considerations and/or modelling.

Data related to simulation and/or optimizations and analyses have been validated through technical-experimental comparison following a simple 3-step procedure:

¹⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

- Criteria. Upstream definition of validation criteria.
- Benchmark. Collection of known experimental data (both from project deliverables and from internal archive).
- Validation. Assessment and reporting on deviations: no numerical data without information on validation has been considered for technical considerations and/or modelling.

5. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Following ECOBULK's Grant Agreement, budget was allocated to cover the cost to make openly accessible the publications and research data in Open Access repositories. This budget has been assessed along the different review meetings and prevision of budget costs for publications have been checked with the partners at the end of each reporting period. The chosen open online repository offers its services at no cost, including the assignation of DOI and the licencing process. Therefore, the cost required to make data FAIR in the ECOBULK project is directly linked with the cost of Gold open access scientific publications, the cost of publication for the Design Guide analysing all aspects related to design treated in ECOBULK, and the effort required by the data access committee to manage the data and the repository and by the partners to facilitate these data. All these costs are eligible under the Horizon 2020 grant, and an approximation of them at the moment of writing this document can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Resources for making data FAIR

Concept	Cost		
Gold scientific publications	7 700€		
Design guide: online and 100 printed copies	3 200€		
		Effort	Cost
Data Access committee effort (UPC)	1.5 PM	7 800€	
Partners' effort for collecting data	2 PM	10 400€	
TOTAL COST		29 100€	

As mentioned previously, the data access committee is formed by members from UPC, who are currently the responsible for data management in ECOBULK. No changes are expected regarding the availability of data after the project end and thus, in the long-term, Zenodo repository will

maintain data and metadata accessible for its complete lifetime. Nonetheless, UPC will preserve the management of data in the repository for at least 3 years after the project end as part of its strategy for the consolidation and creation of project consortiums.

6. DATA SECURITY

The used open data repository, Zenodo, is powered by CERN Data Centre and the Invenio digital library framework and is fully run on open source products. Servers are managed via OpenStack and Puppet configuration management systems, which ensure that the latest security patches are applied. Servers are monitored via CERN's monitoring infrastructure based on Flume, Elasticsearch, Kibana and Hadoop. Application errors are logged and aggregated in a local Sentry instance. Traffic to Zenodo frontend servers is load balanced via a combination of DNS load balancing and HAProxy load balancers. All files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers. For each file two independent MD5 checksums are stored, one checksum in Invenio, to detect changes to files made from outside of Invenio, and the other in EOS for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks. Metadata and persistent identifiers in Zenodo are stored in a PostgreSQL instance operated on CERN's Database on demand infrastructure with 12-hourly backup cycle with one backup sent to tape storage once a week. Metadata is in addition indexed in an Elasticsearch cluster for fast and powerful searching. Metadata is stored in JSON format in PostgreSQL in a structure described by versioned JSONSchemas. All changes to metadata records on Zenodo are versioned, and happening inside database transactions.

Apart from these security measures for data and metadata, the following points are applied by CERN to enhance data security:

- All physical access to data centres is restricted to a limited number of staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties.
- Servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers.
- CERN Security Team runs both host and network based intrusion detection systems and monitors the traffic flow, pattern and contents into and out of CERN networks in order to detect attacks.

- User passwords are stored using strong cryptographic password hashing algorithms (currently PBKDF2+SHA512). Users' access tokens to GitHub and ORCID are stored encrypted and can only be decrypted with the application's secret key.
- Techniques to protect sessions from being stolen by an attacker when logged in are employed and vulnerability scans are run.
- CERN staff with access to user data operate under CERN Operational Circular no. 5.

7. ETHICAL ASPECTS

The ethical aspects of the project cover all facets of ECOBULK's data lifecycle and are described in more detail in the deliverables of Work Package 10 (*Ethics requirements*). Those requirements have been strictly followed by all the partners in the project and data users.

ANNEX A: DATA IN ZENODO

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654805	Injection moulding of composite automotive prototypes	restricted			ECOBULK_MAIER_Building Prototype Mould.pdf	1.59
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Injection moulding 1.xlsx	0.01
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Injection Moulding 2.xlsx	0.02
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Injection Moulding.pdf	6.04
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Moldflow 1.pdf	0.61
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Moldflow 2.pdf	0.55
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Optimization of Injection Process.pdf	1.96
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Set-Up of Mould M30.pdf	5.12
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647346	CWA 17806: Design Circular Framework Setting - Composite recovery design solutions in the automotive industry	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_UNE_CWA17806_2021.pdf	2.99

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647743	CWA 17807: Dismantling methods and protocols in a Circular Economy Framework - Composite recovery in the automotive industry	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_UNE_CWA17807_2021.pdf	3.92
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647313	Circular Design of Composite Products: A Preliminary Framework Based on Insights from Literature and Industry	open	CC-BY-4.0	conference paper	ECOBULK_TUdelft_CircularDesignofCompositeProducts-A Preliminary Framework Based on Insights from Literature and Industry.pdf	0.25
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647315	Closing the loop for wind turbine blades	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_TUdelft_Closingtheloopforwindturbine blades.pdf	1.50
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5653889	Fastener finder toolbox	restricted			ECOBULK_TUdelft_Fastner finder.zip	3.38
		restricted		report	ECOBULK_UPC_D10.1_H - Requirement No. 1.pdf	0.77

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666824	ECOBULK WP10 Deliverables				ECOBULK_UPC_D10.2_POPD - Requirement No. 2.pdf	0.71
					ECOBULK_UPC_D10.3_NEC - Requirement No. 4.pdf	0.44
					ECOBULK_UPC_D10.4_EPQ - Requirement No. 5.pdf	0.72
					ECOBULK_UPC_D10.5_EPQ - Requirement No. 6.pdf	2.86
					ECOBULK_UPC_D10.6_EPQ - Requirement No. 7.pdf	0.87
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666798	ECOBULK WP9 Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_ISWA_D9.1_Project Website operative.pdf	1.46
					ECOBULK_ISWA_D9.3_Project newsletter.pdf	5.14
					ECOBULK_ISWA_D9.5_Project video.pdf	0.97
					ECOBULK_ISWA_D9.6_Massive Open Online Courses and other training materials.pdf	0.43
					ECOBULK_KNEIA_D9.2_Dissemination and Communication Plan.pdf	5.17
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666750	ECOBULK WP8 Confidential Deliverables	restricted		report	ECOBULK_OH_D8.2_Exploitation Strategy Plan and Customer and Market approach.pdf	1.54
					ECOBULK_OH_D8.3_General and individual business models.pdf	3.53

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666718	ECOBULK WP8 Public Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_UNE_D8.5_Report on the standardisation landscape and applicable standards.pdf	1.31
					ECOBULK_UNE_D8.6_Report on the contribution to standardisation.pdf	1.65
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666699	ECOBULK WP7 Confidential Deliverables	restricted		report	ECOBULK_FCBA_D7.2_Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costs.pdf	1.39
					ECOBULK_FCBA_D7.4_Cost-Benefit analysis.pdf	2.20
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666645	ECOBULK WP7 Public Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_CONENOR_D7.3_Environmental technology verification (ETV).pdf	0.87
					ECOBULK_FCBA_D7.1_Design and optimisation of the whole Circular Supply Chain.pdf	1.39
					ECOBULK_FCBA_D7.5_Socio-economic, ethical and cultural repercussions study.pdf	1.27
					ECOBULK_ITENE_D7.6_Legal and Regulatory, Environmental, and Health and Safety Requirements.pdf	5.29
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659874	ECOBULK WP6 Confidential Deliverables	restricted		report	ECOBULK_GRANTA_D6.4_DataBase Management System.pdf	4.27
					ECOBULK_IRIS_D6.6_Quality Assurance System.pdf	2.58

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
 GA NUMBER: 730456
 Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_UPC_D6.5_Decision System Support.pdf	2.57
					ECOBULK_UPC_D6.7_Report on user and system requirements and reference architecture.pdf	3.33
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659842	ECOBULK WP5 Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_D5.4_Solutions of the final sorting of End-of-Life Vehicle Shredder Light Fraction.pdf	1.12
					ECOBULK_BELLVER_D5.2_Dismantling methods and protocols.pdf	2.13
					ECOBULK_CNR_D5.5_Characterization and Selection of materials from MBW and ELV for recycling.pdf	4.77
					ECOBULK_ITENE_D5.1_Report on collection and reverse logistics optimization.pdf	2.67
					ECOBULK_TOMRA_D5.3_Solutions for the final sorting of Bulky Waste.pdf	3.23
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659860	ECOBULK WP6 Public Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_ITENE_D6.2_Sustainable procurement, retail and product tracking and labelling system.pdf	1.03
					ECOBULK_UPC_D6.1_Report on user and system requirements and reference architecture..pdf	0.86
					ECOBULK_UPC_D6.3_End user and stakeholder platform.pdf	3.93

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659834	ECOBULK WP4 Confidential Deliverables	restricted		report	ECOBULK_MAIER_D4.5_Demonstration results of the automotive composite parts.pdf	2.56
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659828	ECOBULK WP4 Public Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_CONENOR_D4.2_Report on (re-)manufacture of the innovative wood based products.pdf	3.57
					ECOBULK_CONENOR_D4.4_Demonstration plans for activities at DEMO SITES User involvement.pdf	9.40
					ECOBULK_NETCOMPOSITES_D4.1_Report on (re-)manufacture of the innovative composite products.pdf	3.42
					ECOBULK_TECHNOPLANTS_D4.3_Report on (re-)manufacture of the innovative nonwoven products.pdf	0.50
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659289	ECOBULK WP3 Confidential Deliverables	restricted		report	ECOBULK_AKZONOBEL_D3.3_Report on validation of sustainable binder systems.pdf	2.86
					ECOBULK_NETCOMPOSITES_D3.1_Report on development of the intermediate materials for composite production.pdf	6.91

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_NTT_D3.2_Report on development of nonwovens intermediate products.pdf	2.08
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659281	ECOBULK WP3 Public Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_IRIS_D3.4_Report on material conditioning processes.pdf	1.45
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659261	ECOBULK WP2 Confidential Deliverables	restricted		report	ECOBULK_GRANTA_D2.7_Report on Baseline description.pdf	3.61
					ECOBULK_ITENE_D2.8_Report on Design Circular framework setting.pdf	2.89
					ECOBULK_TUDELFT_D2.5_Connection and fastener Toolbox.pdf	2.30
					ECOBULK_TUDELFT_D2.6_Prototypes.pdf	12.06
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659233	ECOBULK WP2 Public Deliverables	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_GRANTA_D2.1_Report on Baseline description.pdf	1.96
					ECOBULK_GRANTA_D2.3_Review of material and manufacturing process selection criteria.pdf	3.56
					ECOBULK_ITENE_D2.4_Report on Design Circular framework setting.pdf	1.68
					ECOBULK_TUDELFT_D2.2_Design Circular strategies and tools.pdf	14.28

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659187	ECOBULK WP1 Confidential Deliverables (Version 1)	restricted		report	ECOBULK_EXERGY_D1.1_Governance structure, communication flow and methods.pdf	2.06
					ECOBULK_UPC_D1.2_Management and Technical Progress Report.pdf	10.39
					ECOBULK_UPC_D1.3_Risk assessment and contingency and mitigation plans.pdf	0.29
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5659148	ECOBULK WP1 Public Deliverables (Version 1)	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_UPC_D1.4_Report on additional funding opportunities.pdf	1.56
					ECOBULK_UPC_D1.5_Data management Plan.pdf	0.59
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654956	Life Cycle Cost Analysis for the automotive sector	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_AutomotiveLCC.xlsx	0.11
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654947	DMSO cleaning for component recovery	restricted		report	ECOBULK_NTT_DMSO.pdf	0.26
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654941	MORETTI process data	restricted			ECOBULK_MORETTI_ProcessData.xlsx	1.18

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654933	Circular materials for sound proofing - Experiment	restricted		report	ECOBULK_MICROCAB_Soundproofingnonwoven.pdf	1.15
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654928	Glass Fiber Reinforced plastics waste in wood plastic composites composition for structural applications	open	CC-BY-4.0	thesis	ECOBULK_CONENOR_GFRPcomposition.pdf	6.18
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654909	Construction prototype deployment at Warwick University	restricted			ECOBULK_WARWICK_ShelterConstruction.zip	300.21
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654891	3 Point Bend tests on GFRP material	restricted			ECOBULK_WARWICK_3PointBendtestsConenorcomposites.zip	772.10
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654882	Inventory data for LCA & LCC of ECOBULK's	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_Inventory DataLCA&LCC.zip	3.10

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
	automotive sector demonstrator					
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654862	Waste stream characterization	restricted		report	ECOBULK_TOMRA_bulky waste composition.xlsm	0.01
					ECOBULK_TOMRA_Testing Report 1.pdf	5.00
					ECOBULK_TOMRA_Testing Report 2.pdf	4.63
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654849	Development and re-manufacture of innovative nonwoven products	restricted		report	ECOBULK_NTT_Development on nonwovens intermediate products.pdf	0.78
					ECOBULK_NTT_Remufacture of the innovative nonwoven products.pdf	0.07
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654844	Validation tests on circular-designed table prototype	restricted		report	ECOBULK_MORETTI_Table test 1.pdf	0.29
					ECOBULK_MORETTI_Table test 2.pdf	0.28
					ECOBULK_MORETTI_Table test 3.pdf	0.29
					ECOBULK_MORETTI_Table test 4.pdf	0.29
					ECOBULK_MORETTI_Table test 5.pdf	0.29
					ECOBULK_MORETTI_Table test 6.pdf	0.29
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654829	Validation tests on automotive prototypes	restricted			ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 Assembly.xlsx	0.01
					ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 Dimensional ABS.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 Dimensional PLA.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 Dimensional PP.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 report.pdf	0.38

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
 GA NUMBER: 730456
 Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 Tests.xlsx	0.01
					ECOBULK_MAIER_7791 Weight.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_DEMO Assembly+Dismantling CAD.pptx	4.05
					ECOBULK_MAIER_DEMO Assembly+Dismantling Video.pptx	2.23
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Validation Tests 7791 M48 Accelerated Ageing.pdf	1.06
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Validation Tests 7791 M48 Aesthetic.pdf	1.42
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Validation Tests 7791 M48 Assembly Aerators+Screen.pdf	9.59
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Validation Tests 7791 M48 Assembly Snap Fits.pdf	11.02
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Validation Tests 7791 M48 Dimensional.pdf	3.36
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Validation Tests 7791 M48 Heat Ageing.pdf	9.89
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654819		restricted			ECOBULK_MAIER_Painted Parts 4759.pdf	2.93
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Painted Parts 7791.pdf	1.98

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
	Surface treatment of circular prototypes for the automotive sector				ECOBULK_MAIER_Surface Treatment of Sample Parts.pdf	6.93
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654813	Material characterization for circular automotive applications	restricted			ECOBULK_MAIER_ABS.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_PLA.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_PP.xlsx	0.03
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Recycled1 and Recycled 2.xlsx	0.02
					ECOBULK_MAIER_VirginMaterial.xlsx	0.03
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654791	Tests on particle boards with innovative binder solutions	restricted			ECOBULK_KEAS_Test 1.xlsx	0.01
					ECOBULK_KEAS_Test 2.XLSX	0.01
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654762	Surface activation for reuse tests	restricted			ECOBULK_IRIS_Plasma treatment on CONENOR material.xlsx	0.04
					ECOBULK_IRIS_Plasma treatment on KEAS material.xlsx	0.06
					ECOBULK_IRIS_Plasma treatment on MAIER PP and PLA materials.xlsx	0.09
					ECOBULK_IRIS_Plasma treatment on NTT material.xlsx	0.02
					ECOBULK_IRIS_Plasma treatment.xlsx	0.11

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654749	Characterization of bio-polymer material developed in ECOBULK	restricted			ECOBULK_CNR_TestonTECNAROsamples.zip	60.10
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654723	Characterization of GFRP material developed in ECOBULK	restricted			ECOBULK_CNR_TestonCONENORsamples.zip	38.63
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654713	New binder solutions: KROL 19007 and NARY 19007	restricted			ECOBULK_AKZONOBEL_Calculations for trial KROL 19007.xlsx	0.02
					ECOBULK_AKZONOBEL_Process parameter and recipe.xlsx	0.01
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654693	Compounding of CONENOR material	restricted			ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 1.jpg	3.42
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 2.jpg	2.58
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 3.jpg	3.26
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 4.jpg	3.29
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 5.jpg	3.51

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
 GA NUMBER: 730456
 Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 6.jpg	3.81
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial 7.jpg	3.33
					ECOBULK_AIMPLAS_CompoundingCONENORmaterial Video.mp4	99.64
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654481	ECOBULK promo video	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_ISWA_PromoVideo.mp4	16.99
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734455	ECOBULK on-line meetings' videos	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_April 7 2020 SC Video.mp4	119.42
					ECOBULK_UPC_M36GA Video Part 1.mp4	230.71
					ECOBULK_UPC_M36GA Video Part 2.mp4	38.40
					ECOBULK_UPC_M36GA Video Part 3.mp4	109.50
					ECOBULK_UPC_M36GA Video Part 4.mp4	410.07
					ECOBULK_UPC_May 12 2020 SC Video.mp4	88.58
					ECOBULK_UPC_PR2 EC Review Meeting Video.mp4	438.26
					ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting - WP1.mp4	68.2
					ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting – WP2.mp4	53.8
					ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting – WP4.mp4	274.2
					ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting – WP6.mp4	39.1
ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting – WP7.mp4	107.6					

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting – WP8.mp4	77.4
					ECOBULK_UPC_M54 GA Meeting – WP9.mp4	84.5
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654458	Interviews to ECOBULK project partners	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_ISWA_CRF Part 1.mp4	2.67
					ECOBULK_ISWA_CRF Part 2.mp4	2.81
					ECOBULK_ISWA_CRF Part 3.mp4	3.18
					ECOBULK_ISWA_CRF Part 4.mp4	3.60
					ECOBULK_ISWA_OH Part 1.mp4	1.87
					ECOBULK_ISWA_OH Part 2.mp4	8.30
					ECOBULK_ISWA_OH Part 3.mp4	6.74
					ECOBULK_ISWA_TUDelft Part 1.mp4	3.84
					ECOBULK_ISWA_TUDelft Part 2.mp4	4.17
					ECOBULK_ISWA_TUDelft Part 3.mp4	6.55
					ECOBULK_ISWA_VERTECH Part 1.mp4	3.68
					ECOBULK_ISWA_VERTECH Part 2.mp4	4.34
ECOBULK_ISWA_VERTECH Part 3.mp4	4.95					
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654433	Questionnaire for furniture prototype end-users	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_MORETTI_Questionnaire.pdf	0.12

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654398	Circular products' feedback gathered at Warwick demo-site	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_WARWICK_Feedbackdescription.docx	0.01
					ECOBULK_WARWICK_FurniturePoster.pdf	3.19
					ECOBULK_WARWICK_Manufacturers feedbackShelter.pdf	0.04
					ECOBULK_WARWICK_ShelterPoster.pdf	1.80
					ECOBULK_WARWICK_User feedbackShelter.pdf	0.05
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654287	Interviews with ECOBULK industrial partners	restricted			ECOBULK_OH_Minutes from interviews against CE objectives.pdf	0.50
					ECOBULK_OH_Notes from business models call automotives Maier and Fiat.pdf	0.15
					ECOBULK_OH_Notes from business models call construction.pdf	0.15
					ECOBULK_OH_Notes from business models call furniture.pdf	0.13
					ECOBULK_OH_Notes from interview with KEAS.pdf	0.11
					ECOBULK_OH_Notes from interview with MORETTI.pdf	0.13
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647889	ECOBULK minutes of the Steering Committee	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_SteeringCommitteeMinutes.zip	10.94

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647873	ECOBULK minutes of review meetings	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_ReviewMeetingMinutes.zip	410.79
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647859	ECOBULK Minutes of General Assemblies	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_GeneralAssemblyMinutes.zip	9.90
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734430	General Assembly ECOBULK presentations	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_GApresentations.zip	574.3
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647800	Modular software platform design for supporting a Circular Supply-Chain	open	CC-BY-4.0	conference paper	ECOBULK_UPC_ModularsoftwareplatformdesignforsupportingaCircularSupply-Chain.pdf	0.49
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomc.2021.100137	Structural reuse of wind turbine blades through segmentation	open	CC-BY-4.0	article	ECOBULK_TUDelft_Structuralreuseofwindturbinebladesthroughsegmentation.pdf	1.93

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105393	Structural reuse of high end composite products: A design case study on wind turbine blades	open	CC-BY-4.0	article	ECOBULK_TUDelft_StructuralreuseofhighendcompositeproductsAdesigncasestudyonwindturbineblades.pdf	5.56
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647277	Recycling of GFRP composite: Developing viable products from waste GFRP	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_OH_RecyclingGFRP.pdf	1.86
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647262	ECOBULK leaflet and factsheet	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_KNEIA_Factsheet.pdf	1.37
					ECOBULK_KNEIA_ProjectLeaflet.pdf	5.47
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647251	The ECOBULK project: presentation	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_EXERGY_ProjectPresentation.pdf	1.60
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647243	Volume opportunities for re-manufacturing GFRP-waste: test results & applications	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_CONENOR_VolumeopportunitiesforremanufacturingGFRPwastetestresultsapplications.pdf	2.24

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
 GA NUMBER: 730456
 Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11101604	Critical Factors for the Recycling of Different End-of-Life Materials: Wood Wastes, Automotive Shredded Residues, and Dismantled Wind Turbine Blades	open	CC-BY-4.0	article	ECOBULK_CNR_CriticalFactorforRecyclingofDifferentEnd-us-LifeMaterialsWoodWastesAutomotiveShreddedResiduesandDismantledWindTurbineBlades.pdf	5.33
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647194	MAIER demonstrator dissemination	restricted			ECOBULK_MAIER_DEMO Automotive.pdf	0.20
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Demonstrator.pdf	1.15
					ECOBULK_MAIER_DEMO Questionnaire.xlsx	0.20
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Showroom	1.57
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Showroom0.pdf	1.57

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Showroom1.pdf	2.34
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Showroom3_2.pdf	4.30
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Showroom3_3.pdf	2.79
					ECOBULK_MAIER_Showroom3_4.pdf	7.13
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5647145	Walking the talk towards a circular economy: Advances & demonstrations from the ECOBULK and other European projects	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK_KNEIA_WorkshopAgenda.pdf	0.12
					ECOBULK_KNEIA_WorkshopBanner.jpg	0.88
					ECOBULK_KNEIA_WorkshopSpeakers.pdf	0.78
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5645785	Cranfield University publications in the ECOBULK framework	open	CC-BY-4.0	article	ECOBULK_CRANFIELD_Adhesiveless Bonding of Wood - A review with a Focus on Wood Welding.pdf	0.91
					ECOBULK_CRANFIELD_Alkali-treated Wheat Gluten Cross-linked with Sodiun Alginate as a Bio-based Wood Adhesive.pdf	1.50
					ECOBULK_CRANFIELD_Non-toxic wood binders Challenges and Future opportunities - A perspective.pdf	0.90
					ECOBULK_CRANFIELD_Olive Seed Tannins as Bioadhesives for Manufacturing Wood-based Panels.pdf	1.84

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
 GA NUMBER: 730456
 Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_CRANFIELD_Validation of innovative binder solutions for wooden circular designed products.pdf	45.04
					ECOBULK_CRANFIELD_Validation of innovative binder solutions for wooden circular designed products.pptx	27.72
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5645741	ECOBULK contribution to PolyChar27, the 27th World Forum on Advanced Materials	restricted		conference paper	ECOBULK_CNR_BookPolychar27.pdf	7.78
					ECOBULK_CNR_Polychar27SummaryReport.docx	0.54
					ECOBULK_CNR_PosterPolychar27.pdf	2.84
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5639648	Shelter Design from recycled GFRP	restricted			ECOBULK_WARWICK_Connection details.pdf	0.44
					ECOBULK_WARWICK_Shelter design.pdf	0.93
					ECOBULK_WARWICK_StructuralReport.pdf	1.76
					Shelter design.pdf	0.93
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5639646	Design for structural reuse of wind turbines	restricted			ECOBULK_TUDelft_StructuralReuseWindTurbines DesignFurniture.pdf	1.69
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708570	ECOBULK WP1 Confidential Deliverables (Version 2)	restricted		report	ECOBULK_EXERGY_D1.1_Governance structure, communication flow and methods.pdf	2.20
					ECOBULK_UPC_D1.2_Management and Technical Progress Report.pdf	10.90

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
GA NUMBER: 730456
Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK_UPC_D1.3_Risk assessment and contingency and mitigation plans.pdf	0.33
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5708124	ECOBULK WP1 Public Deliverables (Version 2)	open	CC-BY-4.0	report	ECOBULK_UPC_D1.4_Report on additional funding opportunities.pdf	0.77
					ECOBULK_UPC_D1.5_Data management Plan.pdf	0.62
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5707638	Quality Assurance System (QAS) video	open	CC-BY-4.0	video	ECOBULK_IRIS_QAS.mp4	10.40
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5705516	4WD command frame prototype tests	restricted			ECOBULK_CRF_4WDframetests.xlsx	0.02
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5704913	ECOBULK Reporting Period 2	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_InterimPayment.zip	0.61
					ECOBULK_UPC_PeriodicReport.zip	14.4
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5704903	ECOBULK Reporting Period 1	restricted			ECOBULK_UPC_InterimPayment.zip	0.48
					ECOBULK_UPC_PeriodicReport.zip	7.6

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5704862	Car dismantling	open	CC-BY-4.0	video	ECOBULK_BELLVER_CarDismantling.mp4	50
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5724131	Construction shelter assembly at Coventry University	open	CC-BY-4.9	video	ECOBULK_COVENTRY_Shelter Timelapse.mp4	356
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734265	Design of construction prototypes for the Adventure Park	restricted			ECOBULK_LIPOR_BinShelterDesign.pdf	1
					ECOBULK_LIPOR_DrinkingFountainShelterDesign.pdf	2.5
					ECOBULK_LIPOR_TreeBenchShelterDesign.pdf	1.4
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734398	Codebase for the End-User & Stakeholder Platform and the DSS service	restricted			dss-frontend-master.zip	0.23
					dss-matlab-master.zip	0.05
					eushp-backend-master.zip	13.4
					eushp-frontend-master.zip	1.2
					granta-api-master-windowserver.zip	10
					sso-backend-master.zip	0.05
					sso-frontend-master.zip	0.22
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5735146	ECOBULK Final Conference	open	CC-BY-4.0		ECOBULK Demonstrating circularity for composites in automotive, furniture and construction Part 1.mp4	261.4

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product
 GA NUMBER: 730456
 Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 30/11/2021

DOI	Title	Access Right	License	Publication Type	Files	
					Filename	Filesize (MB)
					ECOBULK Demonstrating circularity for composites in automotive, furniture and construction Part 2.mp4	404.4
					ECOBULK_ISWA_FinalConferenceProgramme.pdf	0.21
					ECOBULK_ISWA_FinalConferenceSlidesPart1.pdf	17.8
					ECOBULK_ISWA_FinalConferenceSlidesPart2.pdf	11.8
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5741733	ECOBULK final promo video	open	CC-BY-4.0	video	ECOBULK_ISWA_FinalPromoVideo.mp4	25